

Supplementary Information to:

Fiber-coupled LEDs as safe and convenient light sources for the characterization of optoelectronic devices

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Supplementary Note 1. Matlab example for automated ON/OFF measurements using the fiber-coupled LEDs

In the following lines we provide the Matlab® script used for the ON-OFF measurements presented in Figure 2b of the main text. The drain-source current is acquired using a Keithley 2450 source-meter unit, connected to the computer via visa-USB. The intensity of the LEDs is controlled using a Tenma 72-2705 Programmable Bench Power Supply, connected to the input of the LEDD1 controller.

The first step is to initialize communications with the Keithley 2450 and the Tenma 72-2705

```
%% initialize equipment
equipment.SM=[]; %Keithley 2450 Source Meter
equipment.TM=[]; %Tenma Voltage Source

% initialize communications
try equipment.SM = visa('ni', 'USB0::0x05E6::0x2450::S/N::INSTR');
    fopen(equipment.SM);
    disp('SM 1 FOUND')
catch
    equipment.SM = [];
    disp('SM 1 ERROR')
end
try equipment.TM = serial('COM1');
    fopen(equipment.TM(1));
    disp('TM 1 FOUND')
catch
    equipment.TM = [];
    disp('TM 1 ERROR')
end
```

Here, S/N must be replaced by the 8-digit serial number of the Keithley 2450. For the code to operate correctly, the Keithley 2450 must be manually set to source voltage and read current.

Next, we set the measurement parameters: V_{sd} is the source-drain voltage, applied to the sample by the Keithley 2450, V_{diode} are the voltages that will be supplied to the LEDD1 controller (ranging from 0 V to 5 V), T_{init} is the time spent measuring current in the dark (in seconds), T_{on} is the time spent measuring current under illumination, and T_{off} is the wait time after illumination and before the following measurement cycle.

```
%% Set measurement parameters
Vsd=1;
V_diode=[0 0.05 0.1 0.25 0.5 0.75 1:0.5:5];
T_init=2;
T_on=2;
T_off=30;
```

Next, to avoid current spikes in the sample, we ramp the source-drain voltage from its current value to V_{sd} in steps of 0.01 V:

```
%% Ramp Vsd to measurement value
V0=str2num(query(equipment.SM, 'MEAS:VOLT?'));
stepsize=0.01;
if V0>Vsd
    stepsize=-abs(stepsize);
```

```

elseif V0<Vsd
    stepsize=abs(stepsize);
end
Vramp=[V0:stepsize:Vsd Vsd]; %define ramp
disp(['ramping sourcemeter to V = ',num2str(Vsd)])
for n=1:length(Vramp) % do ramp
    message=['SOUR:VOLT ' num2str(Vramp(n))];
    fprintf(equipment.SM,message);
end
disp('ramp done')

```

Finally, we proceed to perform the measurement while simultaneously plotting the current in a Matlab figure:

```

%% Do Measurement
for i=1:length(V_diode)
    clear I t
    ind=1;
    tic
    t0=toc;
    t1=toc;
    hplot(i)=plot(NaN,NaN);
    hold on

    % set Tenma to 0 V
    V=0;
    message = strcat('VSET',num2str(1),': ',num2str(V));
    fprintf(equipment.TM, '%s', message);

    % measure OFF current
    while t1-t0<T_init
        I(ind)=str2num(query(equipment.SM, 'MEAS:Curr?'));
        t(ind)=toc;
        t1=t(ind);
        ind=ind+1;
        set(hplot(i), 'xdata', t, 'ydata', I); drawnow;
    end

    % set Tenma to next voltage value
    V=V_diode(i);
    message = strcat('VSET',num2str(1),': ',num2str(V));
    fprintf(equipment.TM, '%s', message);

    % measure ON current
    while t1-t0<T_on+T_init
        I(ind)=str2num(query(equipment.SM, 'MEAS:Curr?'));
        t(ind)=toc;
        t1=t(ind);
        ind=ind+1;
        set(hplot(i), 'xdata', t, 'ydata', I); drawnow;
    end

    % set Tenma to 0 V
    V=0;
    message = strcat('VSET',num2str(1),': ',num2str(V));
    fprintf(equipment.TM, '%s', message);

    % wait for recovery
    while t1-t0<T_off+T_on+T_init
        I(ind)=str2num(query(equipment.SM, 'MEAS:Curr?'));
    end
end

```

```

t(ind)=toc;
t1=t(ind);
ind=ind+1;
set(hplot(i), 'xdata', t, 'ydata', I); drawnow;
end
end
legend(num2str([V_diode(:)]))

```

Supplementary Note 2. Gate voltage dependence of the photoresponse mechanism

In the main text we showed how, for wavelengths below the absorption edge of 1L-MoS₂, I_{PC} depends sublinearly on the optical power density, with $\alpha \approx 0.5$, as expected for photogating-dominated photoresponse. However, as demonstrated in a recent publication, the photoresponse mechanism of monolayer MoS₂ phototransistors strongly depends on the gate voltage: While for gate voltages above the threshold voltage the photoresponse is almost entirely dominated by photogating, this contribution to photoresponse fades away for sub-threshold voltages, resulting in a large reduction of the photocurrent. The remaining photocurrent comes mainly from the

Supplementary Figure 1. Gate voltage dependence of the photoresponse mechanism. (a) Transfer I - V characteristic of the 1L-MoS₂ device for $V_{SD} = 5$ V. (b,c) power dependence of I_{PC} at $\lambda = 660$ nm for two different gate voltages, 20 V above (2b) and 40 V. Solid curves are fittings to equation 1 (see main text).

photoconductive effects, which is expected to show a linear dependence on the optical power density.

Supplementary Figure 1a shows a transfer IV characteristic of the 1L-MoS₂ device and Supplementary Figures 1b and 1c show the power dependence of I_{PC} at $\lambda = 660$ nm for two different gate voltages, 20 V above (1b) and 40 V below (1c) the threshold voltage. The two different regimes can be clearly observed here: For $V_g = 20$ V I_{PC} is clearly sublinear with the power and we get $\alpha = 0.37$, while for $V_g = -40$ V the power dependence becomes linear (or even slightly superlinear) and we get $\alpha = 1.12$.

Supplementary Note 3. Estimation of response time

Supplementary Figure 2. (b) $I-t$ profile of the drain-source current I measured at $V_{SD} = 5$ V and $V_G = 10$ V while switching the illumination on and off at $\lambda=660$ nm and $P_D = 5.2$ mW mm⁻². The solid curves are fits of the rising (red) and falling (blue) parts of the time trace to equations S1 and S2 respectively.

In this section we illustrate how the on-off profiles presented in Figure 2b of the main text can be used to estimate the response time of the studied device. Supplementary Figure 2 shows a time trace of the drain-source current I measured while switching the illumination on and off at fixed wavelength and power density ($\lambda=660$ nm, $P_D = 5.2$ mW mm⁻²).

The response time of a photodetector is usually expressed by the rise time (t_R) and fall time (t_F), defined as follows:

$t_R \rightarrow$ Time required for I_{PC} to rise from 10% to 90% of its on-state value.

$t_F \rightarrow$ Time required for I_{PC} to fall from 90% to 10% of its on-state value.

In our case, the device response is remarkably slow and, in the measured $I-t$ profiles, I_{PC} does not reach its on-state value. However it is still possible to estimate t_R and t_F by fitting the rising and falling parts of the $I-t$ to exponential models and extracting the on-state value of I_{PC} .

The $I-t$ from Supplementary Figure S2 can be well fit using a double exponential model, to account for the fast-responding and slow-responding contributions to the photocurrent I_{PC} . Assuming that the light is turned on at $t_{ON} = 0$ s and turned off at $t_{OFF} = 2$ s we have:

$$I_{PC}(t) = \begin{cases} I_1 \left(1 - \exp\left(\frac{(t - t_{ON})}{\tau_{R1}}\right) \right) + I_2 \left(1 - \exp\left(\frac{(t - t_{ON})}{\tau_{R2}}\right) \right); & t_{ON} < t < t_{OFF} \\ I_{OFF} + I_1 \exp\left(\frac{(t - t_{OFF})}{\tau_{F1}}\right) + I_2 \exp\left(\frac{(t - t_{OFF})}{\tau_{F2}}\right); & t_{OFF} < t \end{cases} \quad (S1)$$

where I_1 , I_2 , τ_{R1} , τ_{R2} , τ_{F1} and τ_{F2} are used as free parameters to fit the experimentally measured profile. We can now extrapolate the maximal on-state value of is then given by $I_{PC} = I_1 + I_2$ and use it to extract the rise and fall times, which in our case gives $t_R = 2.1$ s and $t_F = 20.2$ s.

Supplementary Note 4. Fabrication of the InSe photodetector

Supplementary Figure 3. Optical pictures of few-layer InSe exfoliated onto PDMS (left) and deterministically transferred onto pre-patterned gold electrodes (right).

Thin InSe photodetectors are fabricated by deterministic placement of InSe flakes (~20 layers) mechanically exfoliated from an InSe bulk crystal grown by Bridgman method. To isolate thin flakes of InSe, we first cleave larger flakes of the bulk InSe crystal onto Nitto tape (SPV 224) and then we transfer some of the flakes onto the surface of a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) stamp (Gel-Film by Gel-Pak) by gently pressing the tape against the stamp and peeling off slowly. The flakes on the PDMS can be then quickly transferred onto another arbitrary substrate with micrometric spatial precision by using a deterministic transfer setup. Supplementary Figure 3 shows an optical image of a thin InSe flake isolated onto Gel-film (left) and a picture of the final photo-detecting device (right), fabricated using the same flake after being transferred bridging two pre-patterned electrodes (5 nm thick chromium sticking layer and 50 nm thick gold) evaporated on a SiO₂/Si substrate (with a SiO₂ thickness of 280 nm).

Supplementary Note 5. ON-OFF cycle showing the full recovery to the OFF state.

Supplementary Figure 4. ON-OFF cycle showing the full recovery of the OFF state after more than 30 s.

Supplementary Note 6. Performance comparison between the LED sources and a xenon lamp + monochromator system.

Supplementary Figure 5. Illumination power measured at the output of a 400 μm core multimode fiber (NA 0.39) when using the LEDs (circles, dashed line) and when using a xenon lamp + monochromator system of similar price range and linewidth output (blue line; Bentham TLS120Xe; average FWHM of ~ 12 nm).

Supplementary Note 7. FFT of the dark trace

Supplementary Figure 6. FFT of the dark trace (shutter closed and LED still modulated at 1 Hz), presenting a low frequency region with power law exponent of -0.5 and a higher frequency component of -2.5 indicating that there are other noise generating mechanisms that go beyond the 1/f noise.